

This is to certify that Dr./Prof.

OMAR SAOUD

attended the Congress

Rome,
December 8, 9, 10 and 11, 2022

Rome Cavalieri, A Waldorf Astoria
Hotel Congress Center

UNDER THE PATRONAGE OF

Gemelli

Fondazione Policlinico Universitario Agostino Gemelli IRCCS
Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore

*Say NO to violence
against women*

FLO **Retina** **2022**
IC **OR** **2022**
10th International Congress on OCT
and OCT angiography in Rome

David Rizzo

CONFERENCE SECRETARIAT: **MEETINGS**
Tel. + 39 031 461938 - Fax + 39 031 4890516
E-mail: anna.porro@apmeetings.com - www.apmeetings.com